

IMPROVING AND MODELLING THE ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY OF NCF-REINFORCED CFRP

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ABSTRACT

The poor electrical conductivity of the material causes additional weight and cost in modern CFRP airframes. Especially the conductivity in thickness direction is several orders of magnitude lower than that of metals.

This paper describes a possibility to improve the conductivity of NCF-reinforced laminates. NCFs (Non-Crimp-Fabrics) are widely used as reinforcement textiles for parts produced in infusion technologies. They consist of stacked, unidirectional layers of reinforcement fibres, which are typically held together by a knitting yarn. The knitting yarn allows an uninterrupted path through the thickness of a textile ply. Therefore electrically conductive knitting yarns effectively increase the laminate's conductivity in z-direction.

To demonstrate the potential of this technology, "NCFs" with conductive knitting yarn are produced at lab scale. Carbon fibre UD-fabrics are sewn together with silver-coated, thermoplastic yarns. The stitching pattern is the same as in a typical NCF. The electrical properties of these reinforcement textiles should therefore reflect the conductivity of NCFs with conductive knitting yarn. Different yarn counts and degrees of silver coating are tested. The conductivity in thickness direction increases from 4 S/m in the reference laminate to up to 620 S/m.

The effect of different layups and textile styles is analysed as well. The knitting yarns of adjacent textile plies should be perpendicular (e.g. first ply 0°-direction, second ply 90°-direction). Furthermore NCFs with more fibre layers (e.g. quadraxial compared to biaxial) lead to a higher laminate conductivity.

The second part of the paper describes an analytical model to estimate the laminate's electrical conductivity in thickness direction. A unit-cell of the laminate is divided into zones of homogeneous conductivity. The laminate resistance is calculated as a combination of series and parallel circuits. Model predictions and measurement results are in good accordance.

1 INTRODUCTION

The electrical conductivity of CFRP is much lower than the conductivity of metals. Fig. 1 shows typical values. CFRP is also highly anisotropic. The carbon fibres themselves are conductive. Therefore the conductivity in fibre direction is comparatively high, but still 3 orders of magnitude lower than the values for metals like silver and copper.

Common matrix materials such as epoxy-resin are isolators. Hence conductive paths perpendicular to the fibres are only created by fibre-fibre-contacts. The number of these contacts strongly depends on the fibre volume content (FVC) [1]. Common FVC in aerospace are around 58 %. Conductivities in such laminates can range from 0 S/m to 25 S/m, depending on the architecture of the material and the production process. The conductivity in thickness direction is usually lower than in y-direction, because of isolating, resin rich zones between the fibre layers.

Fig. 1: Conductivity of CFRP and metals (with data from [1])

Due to the lower conductivity CFRP airframes of modern airplanes such as the A350 cannot fulfil all functions that an aluminium airframe does. For example electrical bonding, current return paths and dissipation of electrostatic loading require additional metal to be integrated in the structure. Furthermore unprotected CFRP is at risk to damage by lightning strike. Therefore metallic lightning strike protection is applied on the outer side of the airframe [2]. These measures increase weight and production costs.

2 IMPROVING THE ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY OF NCF REINFORCED CFRP BY USING CONDUCTIVE KNITTING YARN

NCFs (Non-Crimp-Fabrics) are widely used as reinforcement textiles for composites produced in infusion processes, such as vacuum infusion and RTM (Resin-Transfer-Moulding). They consist of stacked, unidirectional fibre layers. The fibre layers are connected by knitting yarn. This yarn is usually made of isolating thermoplastic material. Its main function is to hold the fibres together during production and handling of the textile. The knitting yarn is the only component apart from the matrix that allows an uninterrupted path through the thickness of a textile ply. A conductive knitting yarn should therefore effectively increase the conductivity of the laminate in thickness direction.

In cured state infusion-resins are often more brittle than prepreg-resins. A possibility to increase the laminate toughness are interleaves between fibre plies. These interleaves usually come in the form of thermoplastic nonwovens [3]. Since they are electrically isolating, they further decrease the electrical conductivity of the laminate in thickness direction. When using dense nonwovens that allow no direct contact between adjacent fibre plies, there is no technically relevant conductivity left.

2.1 Textile and Laminate Production

Producing an NCF with any new knitting yarn is costly and time consuming. Therefore small textiles with similar electrical properties have been produced at lab scale. They enable to evaluate the potential of using conductive knitting yarn in NCF. They also allow to assess the effectiveness of different conductive yarns.

Unidirectional fibre layers are sewn together using a sewing machine. The fibre area weight is 194 g/m² per layer. The number of plies that are sewn together varies between 2 and 4, depending on which kind of NCF is to be simulated.

Fig. 2: Reinforcement textile with conductive yarn

The distance between two parallel yarns is 5 mm. The length of the stitches is 2.5 mm (Fig. 2). This is a typical stitching pattern in an NCF. The electrical properties of laminates produced from these sewn textiles are therefore expected to be nearly the same as those of a laminate with NCF as reinforcement. Fig. 3 compares the thread run in the sewn textiles to a regular NCF. In each puncture hole there are two parallel yarns. However the sewn textile holds two threads per stitching line, the upper and lower thread. They are connected by a loop in the middle of the textile. The overall conductivity of NCF laminates should even be slightly higher, because the contact resistance in the loop is omitted.

Fig. 3: Thread run in sewn lab scale textiles and in NCF

The size of the laminates is 60 mm x 60 mm. They consist of 16 fibre layers with 194 g/m² area weight each. The resulting thickness is app. 3 mm. The laminates are manufactured in an RTM-process, which enables a constant thickness and hence a constant FVC of app. 58 %. Therefore the conductivity of the base laminate is constant and the effect of different knitting yarns can be analysed independently.

2.2 Measurement of Conductivity

Quadratic samples having an edge length of 20 mm are cut from the laminates. Before measurement the sample surfaces are metallized in order to decrease contact resistance. In a first step the outer resin surface is removed by sandblasting. After cleaning the surfaces are coated with conductive silver paint (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4: Samples for conductivity measurement

The resistance of the samples is measured using a multimeter in 4-wire-mode. From the measured resistance R the conductivity of the laminates is calculated using (1). The laminate thickness t is app. 3 mm. The cross section A is 20 mm x 20 mm.

$$\sigma = \frac{t}{R * A} \quad (1)$$

2.3 Conductivity Improvement by Conductive Knitting Yarn

Laminates containing different silver-coated yarns have been produced. Yarn count and degree of coating varies. Table I lists the configurations and conductivities.

Designation	Knitting yarn	Knitting yarn orientation / textile	σ_z in S/m	Coefficient of variation
reference	non-conductive thermoplast	intersecting biaxial	4.1	4.7 %
33 biax	33 dtex, standard degree of silver coating	intersecting biaxial	22.1	7.7 %
67	67 dtex, standard degree of silver coating	intersecting quadraxial	34.8	6.0 %
44+	44 dtex, high degree of silver coating	intersecting quadraxial	52.9	3.2 %
110++	110 dtex, very high degree of silver coating	Intersecting quadraxial	621.1	5.4 %

TABLE I: Improvement of Conductivity by Conductive Knitting Yarn

Fig. 5 shows the improvement of conductivity in thickness direction graphically. The reference laminate with a non-conductive yarn has a conductivity of 4.1 S/m. For the 33 dtex silver coated yarn no data for quadraxial textiles is available. The laminate with biaxial reinforcement reaches 22.1 S/m.

Fig. 5: Conductivity of laminates with different knitting yarns

The designation 44+ stands for a 44 dtex yarn with a higher amount of silver applied. The laminate reaches a higher conductivity than that with a 67 dtex yarn having a standard degree of silver coating. 110++ is a 110 dtex yarn with a very high degree of silver coating and hence a very low resistance. The laminate has a conductivity of 621.1 S/m. The bar in Fig. 5 is shortened in order to fit into the diagram.

The results show that conductive knitting yarns increase the conductivity of NCF-reinforced laminates by up to two orders of magnitude. The extent of the effect depends on yarn count and degree of silver coating, which both influence the yarn resistance per length. Using higher yarn counts than listed in Table I would lead to even higher conductivities. However the knitting yarn of an NCF influences some of the laminate's mechanical properties. Thicker yarns lead to bigger fibre misalignments. They increase the size of the puncture hole and cause a stronger out-of-plane waviness. These deviations from nominal ply orientation reduce e.g. the compression strength of a laminate.

2.4 Influence of Layup and Textile Style

Not only the resistance of the yarn, but also layup and textile style influence the laminate's conductivity. Table II lists configurations of laminates with different layups. The results of the conductivity measurements are also shown in Fig. 6.

Designation	Knitting yarn	Knitting yarn orientation / textile	σ_z in S/m	Coefficient of variation
33 biax intersecting	33 dtex, standard degree of silver coating	intersecting biaxial	22.1	7.7 %
33 biax parallel	33 dtex, standard degree of silver coating	parallel biaxial	12.1	15.4 %
33 triax/UD	33 dtex, standard degree of silver coating	triaxial + UD	7.2	8.3 %
67 biax intersecting	67 dtex, standard degree of silver coating	intersecting biaxial	28.8	4.2 %
67 quad intersecting	67 dtex, standard degree of silver coating	intersecting quadraxial	34.8	6.0 %

TABLE II Influence of Textile Layup on Laminate Conductivity

The first three laminates contain the same silver coated yarn with a yarn count of 33 dtex. In the first laminate the knitting yarns of two adjacent textiles are intersecting. I.e. the yarn of the first textile layer runs in 0°-direction. The yarn of the second textile layer runs in 90°-direction (see Fig. 7). This leads to many contacts between the conductive yarns. The second laminate has an identical fibre layup. However all knitting yarns are orientated parallelly in 0°-direction. Because the conductive yarns of adjacent plies are no longer in contact, the conductivity of the laminate decreases from 22.1 S/m to 12.1 S/m.

Fig. 6: Conductivity of laminates with different layups

The third laminate has a quasiisotropic layup. The triaxial textile ($+45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ$) has the same stitching as the first two laminates. The 0° -layer is a UD-ply without conductive yarn. Therefore only 75 % of the fibre layers contain conductive yarn. They are “isolated” by the unpierced 0° -ply. This leads to a conductivity of only 7.2 S/m, which is only slightly more than the reference laminate listed in Table I.

Fig. 7: Layup / textile styles: biax intersecting, biax parallel, triax/UD

The last two laminates contain the same conductive yarn with 67 dtex yarn count. The first one is reinforced with biaxial textiles, the second one with quadraxial ones. 2 respectively 4 fibre layers are stitched together (see Fig. 8). The laminate with quadraxial reinforcement has a higher conductivity, because the conductive paths created by the knitting yarn are interrupted less often.

Fig. 8: Layup / textile styles: biax intersecting, quad intersecting

The results show that using layups with unpierced UD-layers is not effective. The yarns of adjacent plies should always be intersecting. A higher number of fibre plies per textile (e.g. quadraxial compared to biaxial) has two main advantages. Firstly it increases conductivity. Secondly less of the expensive silver coated yarn is required per mm laminate thickness. On the other hand better drapability may call for biaxial reinforcement.

3 ANALYTICAL MODEL TO ESTIMATE ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY IN THICKNESS DIRECTION

This chapter describes a model that can be used to analyse and predict the conductivity of a given laminate.

3.1 Structure of the Model

Fig. 9 shows the unit-cell of an NCF-reinforced laminate with interleave toughening. A complete laminate can be built by copying this unit cell in series. The unit-cell is divided into zones of homogeneous conductivity.

Displayed are the two fibre areas of a biaxial NCF. Topping each of them there are interlayers created by toughening interleaves. These interlayers consist of the filaments of nonwoven material and resin-rich zones surrounding them. There are also zones where the adjacent fibre plies are in direct contact. These areas are essential for the conductivity of laminates without conductive knitting yarn.

Fig. 9: Sketch of an interleave toughened laminate showing the homogenous zones for the analytical model

The electrical resistance of the unit-cell is calculated as a combination of parallel and series connections of the different zones. Fig. 10 shows the circuit diagram. The basic part of it is a parallel connection of the base laminate and the knitting yarn. The base laminate is a series connection of the n layers of the NCF. The resistance of each of these layers is the sum of contact resistance and resistances of fibre and interlayer.

The individual resistances in Fig. 10 can either be measured or are calculated from input parameters. The geometric parameters such as layer thickness or yarn diameter are measured in micrograph images. The specific resistances are gathered from measurements or taken from literature.

Fig. 10: Circuit diagram of the analytical model

3.2 Parameter study

The analytical model enables to analyse the effect of the individual input parameters. Fig. 11 shows the influence of the fibre area weight per layer. The associated input parameter of the model is the thickness of the fibre area (see Fig. 9). However from a production point of view changing solely this thickness means changing the area weight per fibre layer. Higher compaction of a given ply would affect the thickness of the fibre area, but would change its conductivity at the same time.

Higher area weights lead to thicker fibre areas and therefore less “isolating” interlayers per millimetre laminate thickness. The conductivity in thickness direction increases. Three typical fibre area weights are marked in the graph.

Fig. 11: Influence of fibre area weight per fibre layer

Fig. 12 shows the effect of the so called degree of coverage of the interlayers. This input parameter describes which percentage of two adjacent fibre areas is shielded by the non-conductive part of the

interlayers (i.e. resin + nonwoven filaments). A value of 0 % means there are no isolating interlayers, while 100 % characterizes a dense nonwoven or even film allowing no direct contact between the conductive fibre areas. The results show that a nonwoven interleave with an open structure has only a small effect on the laminate's conductivity. E.g. if resin rich zones and toughening interleave cover 60 % of the cross section, the conductivity drops by only 20 % compared to a laminate without any interleave.

Fig. 12: Influence of the degree of coverage of interlayers

While Fig. 11 and Fig. 12 show results for laminates with non-conductive knitting yarn, Fig. 13 displays the influence of the yarn resistance on the laminate's conductivity. The model results are plotted as a continuous line. The graph also contains measurement results from Table I. Model and measurement results are in good accordance.

Fig. 13: Influence of yarn resistance

4 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

Using conductive knitting yarns improves the conductivity of CFRP-laminates in thickness direction. Different silver-coated yarns were tested and conductivities of up to 620 S/m were measured. The conductivity strongly depends on the yarn resistance per length, which is influenced by the yarn count and degree of silver coating. Based on a known yarn resistance the analytical model presented in the last chapter allows good predictions of the laminate's conductivity.

For an effective layout the knitting yarns of adjacent textiles should be oriented perpendicular. A greater number of fibre layers per textile leads to a higher conductivity.

The results obtained so far are from tests at lab scale. The sewn reinforcement textiles only approximate the electrical properties of an NCF with conductive knitting yarn. The next step will be to produce this NCF, which will not only allow conductivity measurements, but also mechanical tests.

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